

MORPHOMETRICAL STUDY OF DEEP PECTORAL MUSCLE IN CHABRO CHICKEN IN RELATION WITH AGE AND SEX

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ABSTRACT

India has the largest livestock population in the world. Meat industry in India is however, still in growing stage. According to APEDA (2019), India produced approximately 4.61 million metric tons of meat, primarily buffalo meat, on a carcass-weight-equivalent (CWE) basis. According to FAOSTAT India ranked fifth in the world meat (373.0 million tons) production, and this increase is due to higher production of poultry and bovine meat. Chabro chicken is a rural meat type bird. It is a cross breed of Barred Plymouth Rock and red Cornish bird. They are active, large in built and are adapted to all climatic zones of our country; hence, they are fit for backyard poultry farming. present study was done with the objective to study correlation of gross morphological parameters of deep pectoral muscle of Chabro chicken with age, sex, and meat quality, of 18 male and 18 female, clinically healthy Chabro chicken, procured from the Poultry Farm, Department of Poultry Science, College of Veterinary Science and Animal Husbandry, DUVASU, Mathura., were divided into three age groups with six birds in each group. The mean volume increased with age in both sexes. The mean cross-sectional area of deep pectoral muscle was 181.67 mm², 290.99 mm² and 336.67 mm² in male bird of 6, 8 and 10 weeks of age respectively.

KEYWORDS: Chabro chicken, poultry, muscle, breast, deep pectoral, meat.

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